

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES

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ToyLabs Integrated Platform Design, Development and Validation - final version

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

ARF	Augmented Reality Feedback
ARFC	Augmented Reality Feedback Component
MTA	Market & Trends Analysis
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PMN	Partner Matching and Negotiation
TCP	ToyLabs Core Platform

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 4.4 titled as “Toylabs Integrated Platform Design, Development and Validation” refers to the final release of the Integrated ToyLabs platform, including all the features and characteristics covering the requirements identified during the project, as well as updates and fixes on the basis of the feedback gained from pilot’s execution and testing.

The deliverable includes for the integrated platform and for each added-value component included detailed step-by-step instructions on how the different functions operate, in a form of a basic tutorial.

Moreover, the deliverable provides technical information regarding the way that the different components have been integrated in the platform, as well as the time-plan followed by the development team for integrating all components in successive development circles.

In addition, D4.4 includes the software validation outcomes, as results of the testing process followed for the different components which constitute the Toylabs platform.

The deliverable is of type “Other”, acting as an accompanying text to the developed software, the source code of which can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and scope

The present deliverable refers to the final release of the Integrated ToyLabs platform, acting as an accompanying text to the developed software and providing information about:

- The final architecture of the Platform
- The integration process and related technical details per component
- The operation of each of the components of the platform in the form of detailed step-by-step instructions
- The software validation process and the tests implemented by the development team before the final release of the platform.

Under this terms, the scope of the deliverable is not only to provide technical details about the platform development but also to act as a document supporting the user in using the platform and its components.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The structure of D4.4 is the following:

- Section 2 describes the final delivered version of the Integrated ToyLabs Platform. Specifically, subsection 2.1 includes information about the platform high-level architecture, the integration process and the operation of the core part of the platform. Subsection 2.2 refers to the added-value components developed in WP3 and describes the way that they have been integrated as well as how they operate in the framework of the system.
- Section 3 refers to the validation of the platform presenting the approach followed and the detailed results of the software testing procedures which took place after the completion of the final version of the system.
- Section 4 concludes the deliverable at hand and the work performed in the framework of WP4.

1.3 Relation to other ToyLabs WPs and Tasks

As the final deliverable of the Work Package, the present deliverable summarises all the work performed in the framework of the WP5 tasks and previously has been presented in D4.1, D4.2 and D4.3.

On the basis of the input received during the piloting (taking place in WP5), the final version of the Integrated ToyLabs Platform has been developed and optimised, taking input from WP3 tasks as far as it concerns the added-value components which have been seamlessly included in the integrated platform.

2 THE TOYLABS INTEGRATED PLATFORM – FINAL VERSION

2.1 Integrated Platform Architecture & Technical Characteristics

2.1.1 Integrated Platform Architecture

The final version of the ToyLabs Platform, consisting of the ToyLabs Core Platform and the three ToyLabs added-value components fully integrated in a common system, has been released according to the schedule defined in the DoA without any significant deviation.

The overall structure of the platform is presented in the following system-architecture diagram, showing the logical grouping of components into separate layers that communicate with each other and with other clients and applications. Layers are concerned with the logical division of components and functionality, and do not take into account the physical location of components.

Under these terms, the ToyLabs Platform architecture can be represented in three layers: (a) the Presentation layer, (b) the Business layer and (c) the Data layer.

Figure 1: ToyLabs Platform Architecture

- The **presentation layer** consists of all the components that implement the interface between the user and the system. A web-based interface has been implemented that presents user-specific dialogs in a browser. There are three presentation components: for visitors, for ordinary/business users and for the platform administrators respectively.
- The **business layer** consists of components that implement the workflow of the ToyLabs methodology. In this layer interfaces/ connectors to ToyLabs

added value components for Augmented Reality and Market and Trend Analysis are included, as well as to the Partner Matching & Negotiation component which although it may operate independently, its interconnection with the TCP is crucial for the efficient operation of the core platform as well.

- The **data layer** refers to the database(s) used for storing all the data required for the operation of the platform. The layer consists of all data-models and data-storage components used in the platform. For scalability reasons most of the components are implemented stateless and depend on input and output data. In practice, all business- and user-related data handled by the Toylabs Core Platform are stored in one database (TCP database), as shown in the diagram.

2.1.2 Integration Process

The integration of the individual components to a common platform has taken place according to the Toylabs platform integration plan which has been included and analysed in D4.1.

Before proceeding to the description of the process followed, the 5 generic integration levels considered in Toylabs, as derived from the Eclipse Integration Conformance Levels¹ are presented here:

- None refers to complete lack of integration
- Invocation refers to launching a component as an external process without sharing data or exchanging information
- Data refers to sharing of data in terms of making data manipulated by the platform to be available to the external component and vice versa
- API refers to allowing components to access platform data through tool-specific client APIs
- UI refers to considering component as part of the core platform as if they were designed as a single application. Although this is the highest level of integration of a component to a main platform, this does not require releasing the platform and all components as a single monolithic. Having a user seamlessly move from the core platform to the component and back is what is actually required in this case.

Referring to the Toylabs added-value components, the target according to the Integration Plan was at the final release of the platform to achieve the highest

¹ <https://www.eclipse.org/articles/Article-Levels-Of-Integration/levels-of-integration.html>

integration level (UI) for all of them, which has actually been achieved without deviations.

As far as it concerns the different releases of the Toylabs Integrated Platform throughout the duration of WP4, a gradual approach has been followed: first, the integration of the Partner Matching and Negotiation component has taken place, in order to demonstrate the related feature based on the partner selection methodology. This early integration proved that a complete process can be executed, including the creation of partners' profiles, the setup of new product development projects, the selection of collaborators and the exchange of documents, messages and notifications. As the component was very close in terms of functions to the core platform operations, the highest integration level (UI) has been achieved even in the 1st release of the integrated platform.

The second component integrated has been the Market & Trends Analysis component. At the early versions of the integrated platform the plan followed was to achieve API Integration level, without proceeding to a common interface. The AR Feedback added-value component has been integrated last, initially at invocation level and then at API level.

Figure 2: Toylabs Components Integration Schedule

As shown in the integration schedule followed, in the 2nd release of the platform two components (PMN and MTA) had already achieved UI Level integration. After that point, any change in the individual components was implemented directly on their integrated version.

In the third (and final) release of the platform, complete UI integration for all the components has been achieved.

In this last release, all final updated versions of the components developed in the framework of WP3 have been integrated in the Toylabs Platform in UI Level so that

a simple user to use seamlessly, in full extend, the platform its tools, without understanding that it consists of different components.

2.1.3 Platform Operation

2.1.3.1 Roles in the platform

In the following table, the final list of the roles that a user can have in the platform is presented. On the basis of comments received during the Interim Project Review, the main update in the list of stakeholders has to do with the addition of the retailer role. Retailers are entities that sell goods to the public and their role in the platform has to do with product promotion and especially with the provision of professional feedback (coming directly from the market and the experience of the retailer) during the product development process. In this framework a product owner is able to search for retailers using the Partner Matching module and include them in any product development process.

PROFILE	DESCRIPTION	VALUE PROPOSITION
Manufacturers	A person, group, or company that owns or runs a manufacturing plant. Companies that are responsible of the whole process of creation a new toy, from its ideation to delivering the toy to the shops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity to produce other people designs, concepts or ideas • Capacity negotiate spaces in the toy stores through their contacts
Inventors	People or companies which offers new toy ideas, concepts or designs usually to manufacturers or distributors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity to create new toy ideas
Childhood experts	Companies or persons which are experts and have the necessary infrastructure to test concepts, designs, prototypes and final products with final users (parents and children usually). The main variables that they use to analyse are: Level of appealing, usability and trend analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree of appealing • Degree of usability • Consultancy regarding trend analysis for the generation of new concepts or ideas
Safety experts	People or companies who are experts in analysing and applying all the safety standards which affects to the toy industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety certification and consultancy of concepts, designs, prototypes and final products
Suppliers	Companies which provides the necessary material, components and/ or machinery required by the manufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass production • Mould creation • Components • Materials

PROFILE	DESCRIPTION	VALUE PROPOSITION
Distributors	Companies which owns toy stores or specific spaces for selling toys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliver the toys to the final users
FabLabs	FabLab is an international concept that started at MIT. The term FabLab is an abbreviation from Fabrication Laboratory and it is defined as: a small-scale workshop offering (personal) digital fabrication.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short series and prototype manufacture
Retailers	People or organisations that sell toys to the public for use or consumption rather than resale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product promotion • Feedback provision

2.1.3.2 Step-by-step operation of the platform

1. Login - Registration - Profile Creation

A new user can register using his name, email address and password or use his Facebook or Google account to login (in which case, the first time an account is created automatically). After the registration, the user is redirected to the dashboard, and is prompted to create his personal profile. This step is mandatory for users that plan to use the platform for more than liking and leaving comment on products.

When a user creates his personal profile (not available when editing), he can set his role in the platform (Toy Manufacturer, Fablab, Safety Expert, Security Expert, Retailer or, just End User). After creating his personal profile, and if the selected role is not End User, he is prompted to join or create an organisation. An organisation (for the platform) can be a company, a group of people that work together (not a legal entity), or even, just the user. In that case, organisation type should be set to Freelancer, and the organisation will act as user's professional profile.

 I agree to the [Terms and Conditions](#)

Already have an account? Go to the [Login](#) page. Register

Figure 3: Register Page

 OR Facebook G+ Google
[Forgot password?](#) Login New user? Register now!

Figure 4: Login page (both using username/password and social login). Facebook/Google login generates an account, if the user doesn't have one.

In case the user has forgotten his password, then by clicking on the relevant link he is being transferred to the password reset screen where he has to provide the email

with which he has been registered and then to follow the instructions in the email he will receive.

Figure 5: Password reset screen

During the first login the User is asked to generate a profile, to utilize ToyLabs. He has the option to skip this part, but without a profile he is not considered a professional of the toy domain so he can only view/ comment/ like the public products, designs and prototypes, but cannot participate in a toy development process.

Figure 6: First login screen / notification to create a profile

In order to create his profile, the user has to fill-in basic personal and communication details and to declare if he belongs in one of the main professional categories which the platform supports.

TOYLABS | Dashboard | Members | About | [Email] | [Bell] | John Doe ▾

Edit Profile

Personal

Name:

Address: Country: Telephone:

Facebook: Twitter: LinkedIn:

Professional

What's the role you have in ToyLabs? Manufacturer FabLab Safety Expert Childhood Expert Just a User!

Figure 7: Editing user (personal) profile

The next step for the user is to identify if he belongs to a professional organisation (eg a company with activities in the toy manufacturing domain). If his organisation already has a profile in the platform then the user may request to join the organisation. If not, the user may create a new organisation profile in the system.

TOYLABS | Dashboard | Members | About | [Email] | [Bell] | John Doe ▾

Edit Profile

Personal

Name:

Address: Country: Telephone:

Facebook: Twitter: LinkedIn:

Professional

What's the role you have in ToyLabs? Manufacturer FabLab Safety Expert Childhood Expert Just a User!

Are you a member of an organization? Yes No, I work alone i Freelancers click Yes, and then choose create an organization.

Has organization already joined ToyLabs? Yes, and I want to join Not yet. I want to create it myself

Organization

Figure 8: Option 1: Joining an existing organization

Edit Profile

Personal

Name

Address **Country** **Telephone**

Facebook **Twitter** **LinkedIn**

Professional

What's the role you have in ToyLabs? Manufacturer FabLab Safety Expert Childhood Expert Just a User!

Are you a member of an organization? Yes No, I work alone [i Freelancers click Yes, and then choose create an organization.](#)

Has organization already joined ToyLabs? Yes, and I want to join Not yet. I want to create it myself

Figure 9: Option 2: Creating an organization

Edit Organization Profile

General Facilities Services & Pricing Certifications & Awards

Name **Legal Name** **Legal Form**

Description

Address

Postal Code **City** **Country**

P.O. Box **Phone** **Fax Number**

Website URL **Instagram**

Facebook Page **Twitter Account**

Figure 10: General Organization Information

During registering an organisation, apart from providing the main profile information, more detailed data have to be provided regarding the facilities of the organisation.

Edit Organization Profile

General **Facilities** Services & Pricing Certifications & Awards

Name	Country	State	City	
Base	Greece	Attiki	Athina	
				Add Facility

Figure 11: Organization facilities (might have multiple facilities in different cities/countries)

In the next tab, the user is called to identify what kind of services the organisation may offer, in which markets has activities, as well as details about preferable terms of payment for providing services.

Edit Organization Profile

General Facilities **Services & Pricing** Certifications & Awards

Services

Geographical Market(s)

Regional National EU International

Competencies

3D Modelling 3D Printing 3D Scanning
 CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation Circuit Production CNC Milling
 Inkjet Printing Knitting Machine Laser Cutting
 Mould Casting Plastic Transformation Sewing Machine
 Soldering Station Vacuum Forming Vinyl Cutting

Toy Categories

Activity Toys Aquatic Toys Arts, Crafts Materials And Related Articles
 Audio/Visual Equipment Books with Play Value Construction Toys and Puzzles
 Costumes, Disguises and Masks Dolls and Soft-filled Toys Experimental Sets
 Functional Toys Game Sets Mechanical and/or Electrical Driven Vehicles
 Play Scenes and Constructed Models Projectile Toys with Launching Device Push-along Toys and Walking Aids
 Role-playing Toys Sand-Water Toys Skill Development Toys
 Toy Cosmetics Toy Musical Instruments Toy Sports Equipment and Balls
 Toys for Babies to Look at, Grasping and/or Squeezing Toys Intended to be Entered by a Child Toys Intended to Bear the Mass of a Child

Production Scale: Prototyping Only Small Medium Large Extra Large

Pricing

Ways of Payment: Bank Transfer Bitcoin Check Credit Card Paypal

Paid in (delay): On Delivery 15 Days 30 Days 45 Days 60 Days 90 Days

Figure 12: Organization expertise, competencies, services provided, pricing etc

Finally, any certifications for the organisation as well as awards received are entered in the next screen. It is important here the information to be added accurately as in order the organisation to get certified, documentation verifying the data entered here must be provided to the platform administration team.

Edit Organization Profile

General
Facilities
Services & Pricing
Certifications & Awards

Certifications

Name	Status	Date
No certifications added		

+ Add Certification

Awards

Name	Date
Dr Toy	Nov 1, 2017 ✖

+ Add Award

Cancel
Update

Figure 13: Organization certifications and toy awards

Each user that has his profile(s) set, has full access to the ToyLabs platform. In the dashboard page, he can:

- Create a new product
- View the state of all his products
- View his active collaborations
- View his archived collaborations
- See his messages
- See his notifications

Dashboard for members with a complete profile

2. Creating a new Product - Concept Phase

Using the appropriate button in the dashboard, the user will be presented with a form for creating a new product. In this form, the user will be asked to fill in a title, a description of the product (as conceptualized), select a category the toy will fall under and the suitable ages.

Then he is prompted to fill information about to whom the IP belongs to (the user himself, or his organisation) and if he wants the product to be made public and visible to the homepage. Finally, the user can upload images (schematics, drawings, concept art or even photographs) and files (budgeting, research material, etc.) for the product. Keep in mind that anything uploaded under the “Files” section is only visible by the product owner (and, if the product is owned by an organisation, the members of that organisation).

The images are visible by anyone that has access to the product: everyone in case of a public product, or anyone asked to collaborate on a design/prototype of the product, even before they sign any NDA agreement. So be careful not to upload any confidential images.

New Product ← Back to Dashboard

General

Title
Enter a descriptive title for your product

Description

Category
Select Product Category

Suitable for Ages From **To**
Select Minimum Age Select Maximum Age i Tentative ages. You can change the age group later, if needed.

Legal

Who will be the legal owner of this product? Myself My Organization

! Do you want to make your product public (can be seen by everyone)? No Yes

Images
For informational images only. If your product is public, these are made public as well

Drop files here to upload

Files
Use this field to upload documents regarding this product. These files are only visible to you, and are never shared with anyone else, regardless of the status (public or not) of this product.

Figure 14: Creating a product

After a product is created, the user is redirected to the dashboard again, where its progress is clearly visible. At first, only the **Concept** phase is enabled. The product owner can edit the product (using the small blue button to the right), and pressing **Continue to Market Analysis** (bottom left) to unlock **Research** and **Design** phases.

Figure 15: Dashboard with a product in Concept phase

Figure 16: Dashboard with a product in Design phase

My Products		Collaborations		+ New Product		Search...
Name	Product	Version	Last Modified			
Robot (Design 1)	Robot Doll	1	01.02.2018			

Figure 17: Dashboard - List of collaborations my organization is participating

3. Design Phase

Any time during the product creation lifecycle, after the Design Phase is unlocked, the product owner (or anyone in his organisation), can create any number of product designs. Creating a design is straight forward. Note that in Designs (as with prototypes later) the “Files” section is shared with collaborators, when one is added to the design.

Create Design

[← Back to Designs](#)

General

Title

Enter a descriptive title for your design

Description

! Do you want to make your design public (can be seen by everyone)? No Yes

Images

For informational images only. If your design is public, these are made public as well

Drop files here to upload

Files

Use this field to upload designs and documents for collaboration with your partners. These remain private, even if the design is made public

Drop files here to upload

[Create](#)

Figure 18: Creating a design screen

Product Designs

[← Back to Dashboard](#)

Title	Version	Last Modified	Actions
1st Iteration of Spinner	1	just now	
			+ Add Design

Figure 19: List of Created Designs

After a design is created, the user has 7 available options by selecting the relevant button as shown below:

Figure 20: Option List after Creating new Design

3.1. Edit Design

It refers to proceeding in any type of edits in the initially uploaded design

3.2. AR Models - Augment Reality Module

This is a link to a page that has everything that has to do with Augmented Reality models. Here the user can see a list of AR models (along with the numbers of downloads, comments and the user average rating) and options to create new ones and edit or delete existing ones. In addition to that, the user has access to an analysis of user interaction for each AR model (clicking on its name), where product owner can what users believe about the AR model. Creating an AR model, requires (in addition to the AR model files) a title and a description and defining 3 feedback categories for the users. These categories default to Design, Features and Novelty, while a 5-star rating system is employed.

After selecting this option, the user can see the models related to the design and then the feedback received for each design/ AR model.

Augmented Reality Models ← Back to Designs

Design: Boeing 787

Title	Downloads	Comments	Rating	Actions
A plane model	15	1	4.56	

[+ Add AR Model](#)

Figure 21: List of AR models

A plane model ← Back to AR Models

Feedback for design: Boeing 787

Play with it

Average Ratings

4.83 DESIGN

4.67 FEATURES

4.17 NOVELTY

Analysis of Responses

Question	★☆☆☆☆	★★☆☆☆	★★★☆☆	★★★★☆	★★★★★
Design	0	0	0	1	5
Features	0	0	1	0	5
Novelty	0	1	1	0	4

Comments (1)

 Marios Phinikettos 3 weeks ago
 Interesting
 Reply Delete

Figure 22: AR model feedback page (detailed ratings plus comments)

Regarding AR-based feedback, the user can either see aggregated information or examine one-by-one the users that participated and the answers they provided.

3.3. Create new version

Archives (see below) the current version of the design and redirects the user to a pre-filled (title, description) design creation form to create a new version of a design. Every collaboration that was formed in current version of the design is archived, and the new version is clear of collaborations (must use the partner matching module to search for partners again).

3.4. Feedback

Opens a page with all the partners the user has active collaborations (on current design) with. Clicking on an organisation, the feedback discussion thread between the product owner and the collaborator can be accessed.

Figure 23: List of feedback received (from collaborators)

3.5. Collaborations - Partner Matching Module

Here the user can see an Overview of his collaborations along with their statuses (negotiating, accepted, archived). Clicking on an organisation name, the negotiation thread is accessed, and (if the collaboration is in negotiation phase) messages can be exchanged. Keep in mind that messages both in feedback and collaborations pages can be accessed through the messages menu (at the top navigation bar, clicking on the envelop icon).

In addition to the list of organisations the user is collaborating with, he can search for organisations to collaborate with. This is done through the search interface in two ways:

- Quick search: typing the name of the organisation in the search field and clicking on the organisation's name
- Advanced search: filling his requirements, and in the list of organisations presented, press the contact button

In the advanced search, the results are ranked and sorted based on user requirements. Clicking the contact button, product owner can message the desired organisation's owner about a collaboration on a design, exchange files (NDA agreements, contracts, schematics etc) and finally add him as a collaborator to the design.

Note here that while every member of an organisation can contact other organisations to collaborate on a design, only the organisation owner can add someone as a collaborator.

Besides the list of products, a user (or his organisation) is working on, two more lists of products appear in user's dashboard (if they exist):

- Collaborations
- Archived Collaborations

In both these tabs, the user has access to designs and prototypes made by other organisations, and where the user (or his organisation) has accepted to collaborate on. The Collaborations tab contains a list of the active ones, where the Archived Collaborations contains (obviously) the archived ones. Both tabs provide access to the product and design/prototype pages of each collaboration, along with the feedback messages exchanged between the partners. For the active collaborations, the user can continue to provide feedback, while in the archived, the message thread is locked.

Collaborations

Design: Boeing 787

[← Back to Designs](#)

[Overview](#) [Search](#)

Organization	Status
FabLab Romania	Archived
Boboto	Accepted
Dr. Sternkopf Media Group	Accepted
Lucía Pérez-Castilla Alvarez	Accepted
Ludicus Games	Accepted
Mathimatiki Vivliothiki	Accepted
Psicoclinic	Accepted
SC Psihoforworld SRL	Accepted

Figure 24: List of collaborators along with their status

Collaborations

Design: 1st Iteration of Spinner

[← Back to Designs](#)

[Overview](#) [Search](#)

Search by name...

ADVANCED SEARCH

I am looking for a: Toy Manufacturer FabLab Child Expert Safety Expert Retailer

That has *any* the following competencies:

<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Modelling	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Scanning
<input type="checkbox"/> CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation	<input type="checkbox"/> Circuit Production	<input type="checkbox"/> CNC Milling
<input type="checkbox"/> Inkjet Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> Knitting Machine	<input type="checkbox"/> Laser Cutting
<input type="checkbox"/> Mould Casting	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastic Transformation	<input type="checkbox"/> Sewing Machine
<input type="checkbox"/> Soldering Station	<input type="checkbox"/> Vacuum Forming	<input type="checkbox"/> Vinyl Cutting

Scale of production needed: Prototyping Only Small Medium Large Extra Large

I will pay using: Bank Transfer Credit Card Paypal Check Bitcoin

Payment will be: On Delivery In 15 Days In 30 Days In 45 Days In 60 Days In 90 Days

Search results

AJU (Not rated yet)
 Safety Expert
No description

[Contact](#) [Add](#)

Figure 25: Searching for partners

Collaborations

Design: 1st Iteration of Spinner

← Back to Designs

Overview Search **AJU**

Important

Before you add someone to your design, make sure you discuss and agree on the terms of your collaboration. If needed, you can use the form below to attach and exchange documents (e.g. NDA agreements, contracts, etc) to help you reach an agreement.

Drop files here to upload

Add as collaborator

Send

Figure 26: Contacting an organization for a collaboration

3.6. Create Prototype

Clicking on the create prototype option, the design is archived and the prototype creation form is presented, pre-filled with design's title and description. Creating a prototype, enables the **Prototype Phase**.

3.7. Archive design

Archiving triggers two actions:

- puts a design in a special status, where the user can only access the AR models and the feedback options
- for each collaboration, asks both partners to rate the collaboration between them based on Quality, Co-operation and Communication. The feedback interface is found in the same page as messages and notifications.

4. Prototype Phase

Prototype Phase is very similar to the Design phase. In this page, the user can generate as many prototypes as needed, and for each prototype has the same options as Design Phase (see above), with the exception of "Create new version" and "Create Prototype" which are missing, and a new option "Move to Production", that moves a prototype to Production Phase, thus concluding the

product creation phase. The rest actions (Edit Prototype, AR models, Feedback, Collaborations and Archive Prototype) work in a similar way as their corresponding actions in the Design Phase.

Create Prototype [← Back to Prototypes](#)

General

Title

Description

! Do you want to make your prototype public (can be seen by everyone)? No Yes

Images
For informational images only. If your prototype is public, these are made public as well

Drop files here to upload

Files
Use this field to upload designs and documents for collaboration with your partners. These remain private, even if the prototype is made public

Drop files here to upload

[Create](#)

Figure 27: Creating a prototype from a design

Product Prototypes [← Back to Dashboard](#)

Title	Last Modified	Actions
1st Iteration of Spinner	just now	

[+ Add Prototype](#)

Figure 28: List of prototypes

Figure 29: Dashboard for a product in prototype phase

Figure 30: Prototype to Production action button

Figure 31: Dashboard for a product in production phase

5. Product Page / Organisation Page

The product page is a page containing details about the product under development, including indicative picture(s). From the product page, the user can easily get to the organisation page where the profile of the organisation who created the product is being shown.

3x3 'V' Pillow Cube for keychain

by VERDES INNOVATIONS S.A.

Like ♥ 1

Ages: 6 yo. - 14 yo.+ | Category: Construction Toys and Puzzles | Status: Prototype

3x3 'V' Pillow Cube for keychain is a smaller edition of Original 'V' Pillow cube, the worldwide breakthrough in the shape of cubes introduced by V-Cube in 2008. The 'V' Pillow's ergonomically-designed rounded lines follow the curve of the hand ensuring an excellent grip and better game.

3x3 'V' Pillow Cube for keychain is small enough to fit on your keys or in your pocket, so you really can take it anywhere!

Images (4)

Figure 32: Typical Product page

VERDES INNOVATIONS S.A. ✓

[About](#) [Products](#) [Designs](#)

Contact

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+302741099280
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[Website](#)
[Facebook Page](#)
[@v_cubes](#)
[@vcube.official](#)

Verdes Innovations S.A. was founded in 2008 and is located in Korinthos of Southern Greece.

Our vision is to provide to people worldwide an opportunity to extend their capabilities and develop pluralistic creative skills through the use of our innovative and educational series of puzzles.

We design and produce our products in Greece and we promote them via a well established and fast growing network of distributors in more than 30 countries. Moreover our products have reached 112 countries via the web. Our best selling markets are Spain, USA, Canada, Switzerland, France, Germany, Netherlands and Greece amongst others.

VERDES Innovations S.A. consists of an R&D division, a production division, a marketing-sales division, a logistic division and a customer support division, of which all strive to provide the best quality control and customer service support possible. All contemporary and safety standards are used in order to accommodate our global customers. Our Management Systems have been certified on ISO 9001:2008 and 14001:2004 standards.

We manufacture so far more than 100 SKUs categorized in 3 major Brands.

a. The V-CUBE™ worldwide patented products. They are a uniquely designed and constructed series of 3D rotational cubes that managed to break a worldwide monopoly for the best-selling puzzle in history. They are manufactured under the unified V-CUBE™ technology, invented and patented worldwide by the Greek Engineer Panagiotis VERDES. V-CUBE™ technology made possible the construction of a Cube with an unlimited number of layers, providing safe and smooth rotation. The revolutionary approach led to an innovative construction that permitted the production beyond five-layered cubes something that was believed to be unattainable for over 20 years! At the same time, V-CUBE™ unified technology has resulted in the design & industrial production of much more durable and user friendly cubes of existing sizes and introduced the "pillow" cube design. Furthermore, V-CUBE™ innovative stylish approach to print directly on the cube's surface introduces border-less creations of popular subjects and effectively explodes the Cube to an infinite level. V-CUBE™ products are classified in 3 different sub-categories: The V-Classics, The V-Collections and the "Create Your Cube" products.

b. The V-SPHERE™ worldwide patented products, a new range of 3D sliding spherical puzzles.

c. The Labors of Hercules, an innovative series of 2D pattern puzzles.

Our products are addressed to kids and parents, students and teachers, professionals and artists, tourists and museum lovers, companies and licensees. Their unique features allow literally everyone to enjoy them and enhancing the puzzle solving experience while offering challenge and stepping level of difficulty.

We have been recognized with several design and business awards for our products and innovations. More information about us and our products can be found on our official websites [www-v-cubes.com](#) and [www-v-spheres.com](#)

Competencies

- ✓ 3D Modelling
- ✓ Inkjet Printing
- ✓ CNC Milling
- ✓ Mould Casting

Certifications

- ISO14001 - Environmental Management Systems Verified
- ISO9001 - Quality Management Systems Verified

Figure 33: Organization page

The page of any organisation within the Toylabs platform, can also be accessed directly just by pressing on the “Members” menu item in order to get the full list of the organisations – members of the Toylabs platform. Note here that only the registered organisations list is available, something that doesn’t stand for individuals as their profile information contains sensitive data.

Figure 34: List of platform members

For any organisation with active participation in the platform, any registered user can get a list of products that the organisation has initiated, no matter in which phase the development is, as long as the related designs or products are identified as “public”.

Figure 35: Organization's (public) products

6. About Page

The “about” page provides information about the platform and links to the project data.

Figure 36: About ToyLabs page

7. Notifications – Messages – Collaborators Rating

Each user may access the messaging system of the platform at any time or after receiving a notification. Direct access to all the notifications received the user can have through the relevant option in the menu.

Figure 37: notifications inbox view

The same stands for the messages inbox of the user, where all the messages exchanged among the user and other platform members appear and can be managed.

Figure 38: messages Inbox view

In the same section that notifications and messages appear, another tab is available named “rate collaborators”. In this screen the user (representing an organisation) after having a complete collaboration with any other organisation can evaluate the collaborator

Figure 39: List of collaborations pending rating (after a design/prototype was archived or moved to production)

2.2 Integrated Added-value Components

2.2.1 Market Trends Analysis component

This component is intended to give the user an easy-to-use tool that will provide him with the appropriate information - through various, intuitive charts- to help him on the one hand identify market trends for his domain of interest and on the other hand gain a deeper understanding of customers' satisfaction and dissatisfaction on specific topics (either products/toys or brands) and as a result on their brand perception, campaign efficiency and competitors' position in the market.

The component works by harvesting data from social media where people express their opinions and have discussions on products/ brands etc. The user that initiates the analysis is responsible for setting the keywords, hashtags, phrases and accounts that will be used for gathering the data. The user is then able to either perform a trend analysis to uncover popular trends in a given domain or collect and analyse customers' feedback as expressed in the web.

2.2.1.1 Integration of the component

The Market and Trend Analysis component was integrated in the ToyLabs Core Platform by expanding the platform's user interface and connecting the engine to the backend as stated in the previous deliverables. As seen in Figure 1, the integration took place in the platform's middle application logic layer through a list of API calls that request specific information from the module. The module's frontend has been integrated using JavaScript and the libraries D3 and AMCHARTS. It is based on the built-in modules of VueJS to communicate with a RESTful API. The module stores its data in a separate database than that of the core platform. Finally, the user initialises the module in the product development's Research phase, which is the second phase after concept definition, and prompts the user to start either a Market Trends or a Social Feedback analysis.

Figure 40: Architecture of Market and Trends Analysis Component

Concerning the component's API calls there are nine endpoints that make API calls; projects, analyses, feedbacks, concepts, parameters, retrievers, accounts, brands and products. Moreover, there are five basic API calls that every endpoint can perform; list, create, read, update and delete that are self-explanatory. However, it should be mentioned that a user will only be able to perform the calls list and read in the accounts endpoint, because this is referring to the social media accounts that the user specifies to harvest data from. As such, a user of the ToyLabs platform cannot create, update or delete a social media account of a different individual/organisation. The other endpoints have to do with the tasks that the Market Trends Analysis component performs and as such can be read, listed, created, updated and deleted by the user.

To summarise, five of the endpoints (concepts, parameters, brands, products, retrievers) can only perform the abovementioned five basic API calls and the endpoint accounts the API calls list and read. For the endpoint named projects, those five API calls may be performed as well as two additional named analyses and concepts that ask for the analyses and concepts tied with said project. Finally, the Analysis and Feedback endpoints handle the visualisations in a Market Trends and Social Feedback analysis respectively and their API calls will be listed and explained shortly.

It should be mentioned that the concepts and parameter endpoints can only be called in the context of a Market Trend Analysis, in which a user may provide specific

meaningful concepts of interest and parameters that will be presented and formulate the visualisations.

The analyses endpoint may perform eight additional API calls that will be listed and explained below:

- **parameters:** Get the list of parameters that are available in the analysis. The "is_enabled" field defines whether each of them will be used to create a separate chart.
- **get_top_hashtags:** Get the 10 most popular hashtags from the documents that are retrieved based on the analysis settings.
- **get_top_accounts:** Get the 10 most active accounts (based on the number of documents published by them) from the documents that are retrieved based on the analysis settings.
- **get_two_word_phrases:** Get the 15 most commonly found two-word phrases in the documents that are retrieved based on the analysis settings per concept.
- **get_concept_timelines:** Daily number of retrieved documents for each of the concepts used in the analysis.
- **get_timelines:** Daily number of retrieved documents for each of the keyphrases_settings defined in the analysis.
- **get_overall_timeline:** Daily number of documents that are retrieved based on the analysis settings.
- **get_parameter_facets:** For the given parameter get number of results for each of the (concept, parameter value) pairs per concept.

Following the same logic with the Market Trends analysis, in a Social Feedback analysis the endpoints Brands and Products can be called. In a social feedback analysis, a user wants to uncover the public opinion about specific brands and products tied with those brands, hence the Brands and Products endpoints. The combination of Brands and Products creates a "Market Set". Market sets are saved in an organisation's profile. When initiating a Social Feedback analysis, the user will be able to create a new market set or load an existing one from a previous analysis.

The API calls tied with the feedback endpoint (that handles the Social Feedback visualizations) are listed and explained below:

- **fget_top_hashtags:** Get the 10 most popular hashtags from the documents that are retrieved based on the social feedback settings.
- **fget_top_accounts:** Get the 10 most active accounts (based on the number of documents published by them) from the documents that are retrieved based on the social feedback settings.
- **fget_two_word_phrases:** Get the 15 most commonly found two-word phrases in the documents that are retrieved based on the social feedback settings per brand & product.

- `fget_three_word_phrases`: Get the 15 most commonly found three-word phrases in the documents that are retrieved based on the social feedback settings per brand & product.
- `fget_one_word_phrases`: Get the 15 most commonly found one-word phrases in the documents that are retrieved based on the social feedback settings per brand & product.
- `fget_brand_timelines`: Daily number of retrieved documents for each of the brands used in the social feedback.
- `fget_product_timelines`: Daily number of retrieved documents for each of the products used in the social feedback.
- `fget_timelines`: Daily number of retrieved documents for each of the keyphrases_settings defined in the analysis.
- `fget_overall_timeline`: Daily number of documents that are retrieved based on the analysis settings.

2.2.1.2 Step-by-step operation of the component

In the present chapter the operation of the Market Trends and Social Feedback analysis component will be explained. Each step of the tool's operation will include a screenshot and a short explanation of the tasks that the user must perform to proceed to the next step as can be seen by the two workflows for each of the analyses that can be performed. These workflows have been sufficiently presented in the context of WP3 and are only presented here to show that the step-by-step operation of the component agrees with them and that all necessary actions have been performed for the smooth operation of the tool.

Figure 41: Trend Analysis workflow

Figure 42: Social Feedback workflow

The following screenshot represent the first screen that a user sees when entering the research phase of a project from the dashboard. If the user has already performed some analyses, they will be listed here by type. In existing analyses users can edit their settings or proceed to viewing the visualisations produced by them by pressing one of the two buttons under “Actions”. Finally, a user may select to initiate a new analysis; either a Social Feedback or a Market Trend analysis by clicking either of the two options at the bottom of the screen. It should be mentioned that Social Feedback analysis is only available for products owned by organisations with configured Market Analysis settings. This will be made cleared in the following screenshots that show how an organisation can create Market Sets for a Social Feedback analysis.

Figure 43: Market Analysis initial screen

When a user initiates a Market Trends analysis, the first screen that he sees can be seen next. In this screen the user is asked to fill in some basic information about the analysis such as the name of the analysis, the sources for data retrieval (e.g. twitter, Facebook) and whether influencer mode will be active or not. The most crucial action at this stage is the selection of the keywords that will be used for data retrieval.

The tool supports single word keywords and phrases that the user wants to exist in the retrieved documents as well as words and phrases that the user does not want to exist. For example, by pressing toy, Barbie, 'blonde doll, !baby the retriever will return text documents in which the words toy, Barbie and "blonde doll" exist but not the word baby. For the user's convenience there is a help text below the keywords field to familiarise him with the procedure.

Figure 44: Market Trends analysis custom settings

Much like in the case of a Market Trend analysis, in a Social Feedback analysis the first screen a user sees can be seen next, and is exactly the same with that of a Market Trend analysis except for the option to activate influencer mode, the reason being that in a Social Feedback analysis the user wants to know the unbiased opinion of end-users about his or his competitor's brands and products.

soft toys feedback

[← Back to Market Analysis](#)

Custom Settings **Time Settings**

Name

soft toys feedback

Keywords

sleeping x soft toy x

Enter the words, phrases and hashtags to be used as search terms. Single keywords are separated with commas. Use ' for exact phrases and ! to exclude a term/phrase.

i For example by pressing toy, cube, 'puzzle toy, !sphere the tool will search in social media for posts that include the words "toy" and "cube", the exact phrase "puzzle toy" and exclude results that include the word "sphere". In other words this search will return results relevant to puzzle toys that are shaped like cubes but not like spheres.

In another example the user could be searching for toys that are shaped like cubes or spheres but are not puzzle toys. In this case the search would look like so: toy, cube, sphere, !puzzle toy

Source type

Twitter Facebook

The data sources to be used for the analysis. Choose one or more among Facebook and Twitter.

[Save as copy](#)

[Update](#)

Figure 45: Social Feedback analysis custom settings

Test Trend Analysis

[← Back to Market Analysis](#)

Custom Settings **Time Settings** Concepts' Settings

From date

30 Apr 2018

To date

30 May 2018

[Last week](#)

[Last month](#)

[Last year](#)

[Save as copy](#)

[Update](#)

Figure 46: Market Trends/ Social Feedback analysis time settings

The second set of settings that a user will be called to choose has to do with the time period for data selection from the sources that the user specified in the previous step. Starting from the current date, the user has the ability to quick select the previous week, month or year as the time period for data retrieval by clicking one of the blue buttons at the bottom of the screen. The time settings screen is identical for both analyses.

Custom Settings Time Settings **Concepts' Settings**

Provide specific meaningful **concepts of interest** (e.g. baby dolls) and **parameters** (e.g. colour, material) that will be presented and formulate the visualisations accordingly in order to be provided with useful and meaningful information customized to your needs.

The **concepts of interest** are terms/ideas that you want to monitor and understand crowd perception and market trends spinning around these terms. The value format follows the same logic as the keywords in the Custom Settings tab.

The **parameters** you need to specify are features on which the concepts of interest will be analysed and compared (e.g. a baby doll made of wood or plastic. The parameter name here is the "material" and the values "wood, plastic"). The value format is comma separated values.

Concepts

Name	Values	Actions
car concept	<input type="text" value="car"/>	
doll concept	<input type="text" value="doll"/>	
greet concept	<input type="text" value="hi hello"/>	
		Add Concept

Parameters

Name	Values	Enabled	Actions
greet param	hi, hello		
			Add Parameter

Save as copy Update

Figure 47: Market Trends analysis concept settings

The final set of settings that a user is called to select in a Market Trend analysis has to do with providing concept's and parameters that will formulate the final visualizations. The concepts of interest are terms/ideas that a user wants to monitor and understand crowd perception and market trends spinning around these terms.

On the other hand, the parameters are features on which the concepts of interest will be analysed and compared. For example, a concept could be "baby dolls" and the parameter could be the material of the toy, e.g. wood, plastic etc. The format for selecting the concepts of interest follows the same logic as the keywords in the custom settings while the parameters' values are a number of comma separated words.

Edit Market Analysis Settings

Organization Configuration | Toylabs Configuration

Keywords

toy x toy doll x

Enter the words, phrases and hashtags to be used as search terms. Single keywords are separated with commas. Use " for exact phrases and ! to exclude a term/phrase.

Accounts

Type	Name	Influencer	Actions
No accounts added			
			Add Account

Market Set

Type	Name	Values	Actions
Brand	barbie	barbie	Add Market Set
Product	doll	doll	

[Cancel](#) [Update](#)

Figure 48: Market Analysis Organisation settings

The final set of settings in a Social Feedback analysis is handled in the organisation's profile as can be seen below. The organisation must fill in the twitter accounts that wants monitored as well as create Market Sets, i.e. combinations of brands and products (that may belong to the organisation or its competitors) upon which the visualisations will be built. The keywords are set in the same way as the keywords in the custom settings of the analysis.

Keywords

toy x toy doll x

Enter the words, phrases and hashtags to be used as search terms. Single keywords are separated with commas. Use * for exact phrases and ! to exclude a term/phrase.

i For example by pressing toy, cube, *puzzle toy, !sphere the tool will search in social media for posts that include the words "toy" and "cube", the exact phrase "puzzle toy" and exclude results that include the word "sphere". In other words this search will return results relevant to puzzle toys that are shaped like cubes but not like spheres.

In another example the user could be searching for toys that are shaped like cubes or spheres but are not puzzle toys. In this case the search would look like so: toy, cube, sphere, !puzzle toy

Accounts

Type	Name	Influencer	Actions
Twitter	cbotsikas		
Twitter	<input type="text" value="Enter a twitter account or facebook URL"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Market Set

Type	Name	Values	Actions
Brand	barbie	<input type="text" value="barbie"/>	
Product	doll	<input type="text" value="doll"/>	
Brand:	<input type="text" value="my brand"/>	<input type="text" value="brand names x brand keywords x"/>	
Product:	<input type="text" value="my product"/>	<input type="text" value="product keywords x"/>	

Figure 49: Market Analysis organisation settings

When the user has selected the settings for the Market Trend analysis he may save them and proceed to viewing the visualisations that can be seen in the following figures. These visualisations include the top 10 accounts and keywords from the documents retrieved and a number of graphs and charts that show the timeline of all results, the timeline of mentions for each keyword/hashtag, the number of documents retrieved for each concept as well as the most common terms for each concept. The last graph shows the number of results for each of the (concept, parameter value) pairs per concept. By using the mouse scroll wheel, a user can zoom in and out of a graph and by pressing the respective button in each graph he has the option to download it as an image or in an excel format for further studying and analysis. Finally, the users that have viewing rights of the analysis can leave comments by clicking on the "Add Comment" button.

Test Trend Analysis

Overview

Settings-based analytics

Figure 50: Market Trends analysis visualisations

Settings-based analytics

Figure 51: Market Trends analysis visualisations

Figure 52: Market Trends analysis visualisations

The visualisations screen after a Social Feedback analysis can be seen in the following four screenshots. The overview section of the screen is much the same as in a Market Trend analysis and contains the ten most active accounts from the documents retrieved, the ten most popular keywords from the documents retrieved and two graphs showing the timeline of all results as well as the timeline of all results per keyword (meaning the keywords selected in the custom settings tab).

The other graphs and charts of the screen are based on the Market sets that the user defined and present information about each of the brands and products of the Market set. Specifically, following the same logic as the previous timelines, the first two charts show the daily mentions timeline per brand and product name respectively while the following bar chart shows the emotions conveyed in the documents retrieved. The tool can detect positive, negative and neutral sentiments in a document and is a powerful tool for a toy manufacturer to let him know how people feel about a specific brand/product. Finally, there is one graph per brand and product that shows the most common one word, two word and three word related topics for each of them. Much like in the case of a Market Trend analysis, the user can zoom in and out of line charts using the mouse scroll wheel and download any visualisation as an image or an excel file format for further analysis.

soft toys feedback

Overview

Market set-based analytics

Figure 53: Social Feedback analysis visualisations (1/4)

Figure 54: Social Feedback analysis visualisations (2/4)

Figure 55: Social Feedback analysis visualisations (3/4)

Figure 56: Social Feedback analysis visualisations (4/4)

2.2.2 Partner Matching and Negotiation component

The Partner Matching & Negotiation (PMN) component is a tool that can be used by users to inquire about collaborators, inside the Toylabs Platform, allowing them to set up formal partnerships, that will lead to collaborative design and development of products.

In more detail, the PMN component is responsible for handling a handful of operations that range from partner searching to matchmaking between different platform users, enabling specific collaboration opportunities.

Partner Matching and Negotiation component is an infrastructure that relies on a three-tier architecture. A high-level description of the TCP architecture is provided in the following figure.

Figure 57: PMN High Level Architecture

The PMN component has been fully integrated, including direct access to the core platform's database, thus, for the end user can be considered as an actual part of the core platform. It allows the user to:

- Search for collaborators,
- Find a collaborator through a parametrized search, or directly using its name,
- Negotiate the terms of a collaboration,
- Exchange files and contracts,
- Form a collaboration, and

- Provide limited access to private product information

Due to the delicate nature of IPR, only the Manager (Owner) of the organisation can add a collaborator to a product, regardless of who took part in the negotiations.

2.2.2.1 *Integration of the component*

The Partner Matching and Negotiation component was integrated with the platform to the point of being considered part of the core platform. This was done intentionally because the collaboration between different organisations is fundamental to ToyLabs.

The PMN creates two new tables to the base database:

- `collaborations`: to store collaborations between organisations, along with its status (negotiating, accepted, rejected, archived),
- `collaboration_ratings`: to store the rating between organisations for each collaboration and to allow better partner matching,

In addition to these tables, PMN has direct access to the organizations' details for searching and is built to use the same messaging system as the platform for exchanging messages and files (contracts, designs, etc.).

Each partner collaboration and each message thread (created automatically for either negotiations or feedback) is linked (through a foreign key in database) to a specific design or prototype.

2.2.2.2 *Step-by-step operation of the component*

As the development of the platform has been finalised, a walkthrough of the component can be presented in order to demonstrate its operation. Indicative screenshots are provided presenting the different screens of the Partner Matching and Negotiations Component and documented in the present section.

1. Searching for collaborators

Any product owner has access to the PMN component through which he may seek for potential collaborators either on new or on existing designs, as shown in the following screenshot.

The screenshot displays the 'Product Designs' panel. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Dashboard', 'Members', and 'About' tabs, along with an email icon, a notification bell, and a user profile for 'Marios Phinikettos'. Below the navigation bar, the 'Product Designs' section is titled, with a 'Back to Dashboard' button. The main content is a table with the following data:

Title	Version	Last Modified	Actions
Design A	1	04.10.2017	[edit] [view] [refresh] [comment] [share] [collaborate] [more]
Aspernatur velit dolore	1	04.10.2017	[edit] [view] [refresh] [comment] [share] [collaborate] [more]
Id recusandae molestiae.	1	06.07.2017	[edit] [view] [refresh] [comment] [share] [collaborate] [more]
Voluptatem enim laborum.	1	06.07.2017	[edit] [view] [refresh] [comment] [share] [collaborate] [more]

At the bottom right of the table, there is a '+ Add Design' button. A 'Collaborations' dropdown menu is shown over the 'Actions' column of the first row.

Figure 58: Product Designs Panel

2. Searching potential collaborators

A user of Toylabs Platform can search for a partner to collaborate either directly by providing the name of a specific company/ organisation participating in the platform or by defining certain criteria. The two options are being demonstrated in the figures below.

Figure 59: Search by certain criteria screen

Figure 60: Search by name screen

3. Criteria Matching

On the basis of the criteria defined, a list of organisations/ experts which cover them is being presented. The user has the opportunity to review all available information coming from the profile of each potential collaborator and after choosing the one which covers all parameters a negotiation session begins.

Negotiation takes place through a direct secure messaging system allowing the exchange of specific documents, like an NDA Agreement which is considered as very important to be signed from both parties, technical documents in order to define exact needs, financial offers and at the end exchange of contacts setting up the collaboration.

The user can start the negotiation session for a new collaboration by pressing the “Contact” button. After a successful negotiation, as well as in specific cases that no negotiation is needed (like when a collaboration contract already exists among the two partners), an agreed collaboration is being introduced for a specific design or prototype by pressing the “Add” button, as seen in the next screenshot.

Figure 61: Initiating a collaboration

4. The terms of the collaboration

Before adding someone to a collaboration, certain terms are being discussed and negotiated. An exchange of documents (NDA agreement, contracts, etc.) can be used, so that the interested parties reach an agreement.

Figure 62: Negotiation of the terms and Exchange of contracts

5. Joining a collaboration

The next screenshot shows a user added as a collaborator to an existing design/ prototype model.

Figure 63: Adding as a collaborator

As long as a new partner is being introduced as collaborator in a specific design or prototype, all privately-shared data regarding the toy under development become available to him. The actual collaboration (in terms of technical work) does not of course take place in the platform, however all files, designs and technical documents are exchanged and monitored through the platform. In order to help in more fruitful collaborations avoiding conflicts, all activities are being timestamped in

the platform, making it easy to identify which is the case when any disagreement appears between two collaborators.

2.2.3 Augmented Reality Feedback component

The Augmented Reality Feedback Component (ARF Component or ARFC) is a tool used to present 3D models to users (both professionals and end-users), and to allow them to interact with toys early in the production cycle. This gives the manufacturers the advantage to get feedback and improve their product designs, saving them both money and time.

The ARFC consists of 3 different sub-modules: Augmented Reality system for model presentation and interaction, Voting and Feedback system for obtaining feedback from user, and Feedback Evaluation system, used by product owners for evaluating the results, so they can enhance their product designs.

2.2.3.1 Architecture

At the time the present deliverable is being compiled, the Augmented Reality Feedback is fully integrated in the Toylabs platform, in respect to the integration plan provided in D4.2.

The following figure represents the architecture of the component, showing in a clear way both the different screens as part of ARF user interface and the connectors to the core platform at application logic layer.

Figure 64: ARF High Level Architecture

2.2.3.2 Integration of the component

The Augmented Reality Feedback component, due to the need for a mobile application, has a more complex integration (as can be seen from its architecture) than other components.

In the ToyLabs Core Platform there's the sub-module that allows product owners to upload Augmented Reality (AR) models, to define questions for the AR app users and to view and analyze the feedback of those users. The integration took place in the platform's middle application logic layer through a list of (internal) API calls that request and save specific information to the sub-module. The sub-module's frontend is based on the build-in modules of VueJS. Finally, the user can initialize the module from any Design or Prototype he (or his organization) owns, thus making it available in both the Design and the Prototype phases.

To compliment the integration with the platform, an iOS application is provided. The application communicates with the platform to get access to AR models and submit feedback to the product owner, through a RESTful API:

- `login`: Used to *post* user's email and password to the platform to login and obtain a token to sign all other requests and identify the user.
- `user`: Used to *get* user information (name, avatar, organizations, etc.)
- `ar-models`: Used to *get* a list of all AR models the user has access to. This includes user's own models, user organizations' models and models that belong to designs and prototypes the user (or his organization) is working (collaborating) on.
- `ar-model/{id}/download`: Gets the information for a specific AR model.
- `ar-model/{id}/questions`: Used to *get* a list of questions to be presented to the user after using the AR model, for providing feedback to the product owner.
- `ar-model/{id}/feedback`: Used to *post* user's feedback to the backend. Feedback includes both answer to the questions (from a scale 1 to 5), and free text comments.

`file/{id}`: Downloads model files for a specific AR model.

2.2.3.3 Step-by-step operation of the component

1. Product Owner perspective

- The product owner can attach to each Design (or Prototype - the Augmented Reality module is available for both Designs and Prototypes in the exact same way), one or more AR models for getting feedback on that asset (Design or Prototype). We tried to make the process as easy and quick as possible, because we believe that AR is an invaluable part while designing a new toy, and a way to differentiate the ToyLabs platform from any generic collaboration platforms available.
- Any user of the product owning organization, can access the AR models page for a Design using the 'eye' icon in the design actions. On that page, the user can see all models attached to that design and can edit or delete them (any feedback provided by end-users or collaborators is lost when a model is deleted).

Figure 65: Access to AR Models Page

- For each model, an overview that includes Number of Downloads, Average Rating and Number of Comments received so far is provided.
- Clicking on a model, a full analysis of what users believe, is presented to the user. On this page, the product owner can see average rating for each question asked, a breakdown of the ratings per question and rating given and the comments provided by the users.

Hurray! My second AR model!

Feedback for design: Lorem

[← Back to AR Models](#)

Some text can go here as well!

Average Ratings

4.33 MY DESIGN

3.67 SUPER FEATURES

3.67 NOVELTY

Analysis of Responses

Question	★ ★ ★ ★ ★	★ ★ ★ ★ ☆	★ ★ ★ ☆ ☆	★ ★ ★ ☆ ☆	★ ★ ★ ☆ ☆
My Design	0	0	1	0	2
Super Features	0	1	0	1	1
Novelty	1	0	0	0	2

Comments (2)

Marios Phinikettos 1 week ago
 Test comments!
[Reply](#) [Delete](#)

Marios Phinikettos 1 week ago
 Testing API feedback!
[Reply](#) [Delete](#)

Figure 66: Breakdown of Rating by questions

- As above, creating an AR model for a design is as straight forward as choosing the “Create AR model” in the AR models page, filling a quick form and uploading the model files.

Create AR Model

[← Back to AR Models](#)

Title

Enter a descriptive title for your AR model

Description

Use this field to explain to users:

- what to expect,
- how to use the model,
- possible shortcomings,
- what to test,
- whatever you think is necessary to know before they use the model.

Files

For the model to work correctly, all the nodes of the 3D model should be under a parent node and that parent node should have the exact same name as the filename of the model. Keep in mind that, when opened in the ToyLabs app, the front of the model will be displayed, so make sure it is designed accordingly. **Supported file types:** fbx, obj, 3ds, stl, dae, stl (and image files for use as textures).

Drop files here to upload

Questions

Users that download your AR model will be asked to rate it based on a number of criteria (change to suit your specific needs). Rating will be done using a scale of 1-5.

Question 1	Design
Question 2	Features
Question 3	Novelty

Figure 67: Create AR Model Screen with uploading Files option and Creating questions Panel

- For each model, the user is asked to provide a short title of the model (this is how the model will be listed in the ToyLabs app), enter a description for the user and enter 3 questions that can be answered using a 5-star rating system. The description can be an explanation to the users about what this toy is about, how to use the model, what kind of feedback is expected from them etc. Remember, the AR models are not to be used for finished products (even though that's possible), but for getting feedback from collaborators (usually child and security experts) early on the toy creation process.

Augmented Reality Models

Design: Lorem

[← Back to Designs](#)

Title	Downloads	Comments	Rating	Actions
Hurray! My second AR model!	1	2	3.89	
gbikas ar	2	1	3.33	
Cherub test	1	4	3.25	
cherub dae	0	0	0.00	
new dae file	0	0	0.00	
neww dae	2	1	3.67	

[+ Add AR Model](#)

Figure 68: List of Augmented Reality Models

2. End User (Provider of feedback) perspective

- The User opens the Toylabs mobile app. The login screen is presented. User has three options to authenticate (email, Facebook, google).

Figure 69: Augmented Reality Mobile Tool User Access

- After successful login, user is redirected to the main view of the app, where he can see a list of AR models (title, average rating, thumbnail). These include models that belong to (a) public products, (b) public designs or prototypes, (c) their own (or their organisations') products and (d) designs or prototypes they are collaborating on.
By tapping the top left button, user can sort the list by title, average rating or date.

Figure 70: Augmented Reality Mobile Tool – AR Model Selector

- After an AR-model of the list is selected, the user is presented with the details of that ar-model. User can download the ar-model file (or delete it).

Figure 71: Augmented Reality Tool – Model Description

- By tapping the “Open AR Camera” button, the camera of the phone is activated. User has to wait 2-3 seconds in order to allow the AR camera to orient itself.

The user can tap anywhere in the screen and the AR model will be placed in that place. The model is anchored to the specific point the user tapped, so the user can go around the model and observe it. If he taps on the already placed model, then it disappears. When user finishes observing the AR model, he taps the “Rate Model” button and he is presented with the questionnaire.

Figure 72: Augmented Reality Mobile Tool – AR Viewer

- User must rate 3 questions by selecting an amount of stars (1-5) for each question. Afterwards the user has the option to leave a comment and then tap submit.

Figure 73: Augmented Reality Mobile Tool – Rating questions Screenshots

- In order to logout, user must go back to the main view and tap his profile pic in the top right corner. User is presented with his profile view, in which he has the option to logout.

Figure 74: Augmented Reality Mobile Tool – User Profile View

3 TOYLABS PLATFORM VALIDATION

3.1 Final Validation of the Platform

3.1.1 Validation Approach

In deliverable D4.3, the platform's validation approach was presented and explained, having as reference the Software Product Quality Evaluation Reference Model that describes the process, activities and tasks performed during the quality evaluation of a software product. This reference model is defined by the standard ISO/IEC 25040 that contains general requirements for specification and evaluation of software quality and clarifies the general concepts providing a process description for evaluating quality of software product stating the requirements for the application of the evaluation process.

The model that for the platform validation was sufficiently covered in the D4.3. As such, in the present chapter a short reminder of Test Cases in software development is given, as well as the template of the Test Cases that will be used for the validation of the ToyLabs platform. It should be mentioned, that the main contribution of the present chapter are the validation results, i.e. the actual results of the Test Case scenarios that were set in the previous deliverable and whether they covered their respective requirements.

A test case is a set of test inputs, execution conditions, and expected results developed for a particular objective: to exercise a particular program path or verify compliance with a specific requirement. Test cases are necessary to verify successful and acceptable implementation of the product requirements. The evaluation team proposed to use a three-step process for generating ToyLabs test cases. For each ToyLabs use case a full set of use-case scenarios have already been generated in the context of WP2. These scenarios were later used to define the platform's requirements depending on the type of user, the specific module being used as well as the phase of the toy development process.

The template of the test case is reported below. The test case template includes a test case ID and the test scenario description. The ID is a simple incremental number to make the test case easy to identify. The scenario is the textual description of the test case objective.

The main part of the test case is correlated to the steps; for each line:

- Step ID: provides the incremental step identifier (independently from the test case ID)
- Test Step: provides the information for the tester about what to do
- Test Data: data to insert when applicable

- Expected Results: the result that the system should return having as input the action and the test data. Result can be a number, a behaviour, a state or even an error
- Actual Result: evaluation of results
 - Yes: the result is the one expected
 - Partial: there are troubles but the user can progress anyway in the process
 - No: the result is wrong or the user is not able to progress

Test Case TU01 ID				
Test Case Scenario	Log in the platform			
Step ID	Test Step	Test Data	Expected Results	Actual Results
ID01	1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/ 2. Enter username and password	User's credentials	User successfully logs in to the platform	Yes Partial No

Table 1: Test case Template and Example

Results are summarized in the following table as follows:

- Test Case ID: same as test case
- Test Scenario: same as test case
- Test Data: summary of data in the test case
- Expected results: result of the overall test case
- Actual result: actual result of the overall test case
- Pass/Fail: evaluation of the overall test case, the options being Yes, Partial or No

3.1.2 Final Validation Results

ToyLabs Core Platform						
Test Case ID	Test Scenario	Test Steps	Test Data	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
ID01	User registration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/ 2. Click on the Register button 3. Enter required information correctly 4. Press "Register" button 	Username E-mail Password x2	<p>Successful registration if user enter information correctly</p> <p>Unsuccessful registration if user failed to enter required information correctly</p>	<p>Successful registration if information was filled correctly. User is then asked to edit his profile</p> <p>If any of the information was not filled correctly the registration is unsuccessful and the user is asked to fill it properly</p>	Yes
ID02	Log in/ Log out	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/ 2. Click on the Log In button 3. Enter required information correctly 4. Press "Log In" button 5. Press "Log Out" button to log out 	Username Password OR Facebook account OR Google+ account	<p>Successful Log in if user enter information correctly</p> <p>Unsuccessful Log in if user failed to enter required information correctly</p> <p>Successful Log out in every case</p>	<p>Successful login and user redirected to his Dashboard</p> <p>Unsuccessful login if information was not filled correctly. Message saying these credentials do not</p>	Yes

					<p>match our records</p> <p>Successful logout in every case. User redirected to the platform's homepage as a guest</p>	
ID03	Edit profile	<p>1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/profile/edit</p> <p>2. Edit personal information</p> <p>3. Join or create an organisation</p> <p>4. Click on the "Update" button</p>	Various personal information	<p>Successful update of personal information by clicking the "Update" button</p> <p>Cancellation of all changed information by pressing the "Cancel" button</p>	<p>Successful update of personal information by clicking the update button.</p> <p>Cancellation of changes by clicking cancel.</p> <p>In any case user is redirected to his dashboard.</p>	Yes
ID04	Members	<p>1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/organizations</p> <p>2. View a list of all registered organisations in the platform</p>	-	Successful loading of the organisations page	<p>Loading of the member page where user sees the list of platform members.</p> <p>The user can see the profile of the members by clicking their name.</p>	Yes
ID05	Public projects	<p>1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu</p> <p>2. Click on any public project</p>	-	Successful loading of public projects, ability to like	Public projects are shown at the Home page and the user may like	Yes

		3. View information/ images about project 4. Like and comment		and comment	and comment if he wishes.	
ID06	Dashboard	1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/dashboard 2. View a list of all ongoing projects 3. Create a new project by clicking on the “New product” button 4. View personal messages and notifications 5. Search for a project	-	Successful loading of dashboard and all of its functionalities	Successful loading of the dashboard. The user can see all of his ongoing projects and enter the phase that he desires in the development process.	Yes
ID07	Rating System	1. Click on a collaborator profile 2. Rate said collaborator	-	Successful rating of organisation	Successful rating of organisation	Yes
ID08	Project Creation	1. Click on the “New Product” button 2. Enter title and description 3. Choose the product category 4. Choose the age groups 5. Choose the legal owner of the product 6. Choose if the product will be public 7. Add Images and Files	Product general information, images, files	Successful creation of new product	Successful creation of new product, selection of toy category, age groups, legal owner and ability to upload images and files	Yes

		8. Press the "Create" button				
ID09	Design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on the "Design" tab 2. Click on the "Add Design" button 3. Enter title, description and choose if the design will be public 4. Add images and files 5. Press the "Create" button 	Design general information, images, files	Successful creation of new design	Successful creation of new design	Yes
ID10	Edit design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on the "Edit Design" button 2. Update information 3. Click on the "Update" button 		Ability to edit a design	User can edit a design by pressing the edit button unless the design is archived.	Yes
ID11	Create new design version	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on the "Create New Version" button 2. Click Yes when prompted 3. Old design is archived 	Updated design information	Successful creation of new version and archiving of old	Successful creation of new version and archiving of old. Archived designs can only be viewed	Yes
ID12	Create new prototype	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on the "Prototype" tab 2. Click on the "Add Prototype" button 3. Enter title, description and choose if 	Prototype information, images and files	Successful creation of a prototype	Successful creation of a prototype	Yes

		the prototype will be public 4. Add images and files 5. Press the "Create" button				
ID10	Edit Prototype	1. Click on the "Edit Prototype" button 2. Update information 3. Click on the "Update" button		Ability to edit a prototype at will	Successful edit of a prototype unless it is archived	Yes
ID11	Move prototype to production	1. Click on the "Move to Production" button 2. Product is ready to be produced	Working prototype	Product development ends and production begins. The platform has no role in the production which is handled internally	Product is successfully moved in the production phase	Yes

Table 2: ToyLabs Core Platform Validation / Tests

ToyLabs Market and Trends Analysis Component						
Test Case ID	Test Scenario	Test Steps	Test Data	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
ID01	Initialise module	1. Navigate to https://platform.toylabs.eu/dashboard 2. Click on the Research button 3. Choose between Market Trends or Social	-	Successful initialization of Market Trends & Social Feedback module	Module is initialised successfully for both modes	Yes

		Feedback Analysis				
ID02	Custom settings	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click the Custom Settings tab 2. Name the analysis 3. Enter keywords to be used as search terms 4. Select social media channels 5. Enable/disable influencers mode 	<p>Analysis name</p> <p>Words, phrases, hashtags to be used as search terms</p>	Successful loading of custom settings page. Ability to modify the custom settings	Custom settings are loaded successfully . In a social feedback analysis no influencer mode option exists as intended	Yes
ID03	Time settings	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click the Time Settings tab 2. Enter from and to dates 3. Alternatively click the “Last week”, “Last month” or “Last year” buttons 	Time period for data harvesting	<p>Successful loading of time settings</p> <p>Successful setting of from and to dates when pressing the “Last week”, “Last month” or “Last year” buttons</p>	<p>Successful loading of time settings</p> <p>The choices for last week, month and year count successfully from the present day</p>	Yes
ID04	Concept's settings	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click the Concept's Settings tab 2. Add concepts and values for them 3. Add parameters and value for them 	Concepts, parameters that will formulate the visualisations	<p>Successful loading of Concept's Settings</p> <p>Correct visualisations according to concepts and parameters defined</p>	<p>Successful loading of the page.</p> <p>Concept's and parameters are visualised correctly</p>	Yes
ID05	Create analysis	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click the Create button 	-	Successful creation of analysis	Successful creation of analysis	Yes

ID06	Edit analysis	1. Click the "Edit Analysis" button 2. Modify analysis 3. Save as copy or update	-	Successful update of analysis	Analysis can be edited at any point and the visualisations will be updated	Yes
ID07	See visualized analytics	1. Click the "View Analysis" button 2. View visualised analytics	-	Successful loading of visualisations according to the user's settings	Visualisation page is loaded	Yes

Table 3: MTA Component Validation / Tests

ToyLabs Partner Matching and Negotiation Component						
Test Case ID	Test Scenario	Test Steps	Test Data	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
ID01	Initialise module	1. Navigate to Design or Prototype stage 2. Click on the Collaborations button next to a design or prototype 3. See an overview of all discussions or search for a new partner	-	Successful initialization of Partner Matching module	Successful initialization of Partner Matching module	Yes
ID02	Search for partner	1. Click the Search tab 2. Search by name Or 3. Use advanced search 4. Choose type of	Partner name or information to search for one	List of suitable partners is showed correctly	Successful search for partners. List of suitable partners according to the criteria	Yes

		partner, competencies, scale of production needed, payment method and time 5. Click the "Search" button			filled is shown	
ID03	Overview	1. Click on the "Overview" tab 2. Invite a partner to a step of the process 3. Select suitable partners 4. Accept or decline responses		Successful handling of all partner matching related tasks	Successful management of all partner matching tasks through an easy to use interface	Yes

Table 4: PMN Component Validation / Tests

ToyLabs AR Feedback Component						
Test Case ID	Test Scenario	Test Steps	Test Data	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
ID01	Initialise module	1. Navigate to Design or Prototype stage 2. Click on the "AR Models" button next to a design or prototype 3. See an overview of all AR models or add a new one	-	Successful initialization of Augmented Reality module	Successful initialization of Augmented Reality module both for the creator of a prototype but also through the mobile app for end-users	Yes

ID02	Add AR model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click the "Add AR Model" tab 2. Enter title and description 3. Add files of the correct format 4. Choose the criteria that users will be asked to rate when downloading the AR model 5. Click on the "Create" button 	AR model information, images and files	Successful creation of AR model	<p>Successful creation of AR model</p> <p>AR model is loaded correctly in the mobile app and users have the ability to project it in their space, answer a questionnaire and leave feedback</p>	Yes
ID03	Overview	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on the "AR Models" button next to a design or prototype 2. See an overview of all AR models 3. View number of downloads, Comments and mean rating 4. Accept or decline responses 	-	Successful viewing of all AR models and relevant information	Successful viewing of all AR models and relevant information	Yes
ID04	Edit AR model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on the "Edit AR Model" button next to an AR model 2. Modify information and files 3. Click on the "Update" button 	-	Successful update of AR model	User can edit an AR model of a prototype as long as the prototype is not archived	Yes

ID05	Delete AR model	1. Click on the "Delete AR Model" button next to an AR model 2. Click Yes when prompted	-	Successful deletion of AR model	Successful deletion of AR model	Yes
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Table 5: Toy labs ARF Component Validation / Tests

4 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable D4.4 describes the structure, the integration details and the operational assets of the final version of the Toylabs Integrated Platform, incorporating all the components developed in the framework of WP3 and presented in Deliverable D3.5.

The final version of the Toylabs Integrated Platform has been developed on the basis of the feedback received on the previous releases by the end / pilot users of the system during the piloting phase of the project as well as during the meetings performed with the consortium partners in order to discuss live on the usage of the platform and potential identify functional changes/ optimizations to perform.

The present document provides technical, functional and architectural details regarding the way that the individual components have been integrated in a common platform. At the same time, the document is also addressed to potential end users as detailed step-by-step instructions are included for how each function/ module of the platform operates.

Finally, the testing approach followed and catalogues of tests which have been performed in the framework of the validation of the software are also included in the deliverable as validation has been a core part of the work performed within WP4.

At the end of the project, the Toylabs Integrated Platform can be definitely considered as a mature software product, fully operational and thoroughly tested. Of course, in the post-exploitation phase, which is the period after the end of the project that the technical partners plan to continue supporting and assist in the evolution of the platform, further improvements maybe introduced on the basis of needs expressed by the Toylabs users, referring not only to the consortium partners but to all the active members/ users of the Toylabs platform. While most of such needs are expected to refer to the added value components which are integrated in the platform, any update to a component leads to a new version of the whole platform as well as to a regression testing process in order to verify that no issues have been raised to the operation of the platform due to the update of the component.

In any case, the documented source code of the platform shall remain open-source and available in the code repository of the project, managed by Singular Logic, publicly accessible in the following url: <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>.